

Supplementary Material 1

Scholarly Databases and Journal Library

Cereal yield, yield stability, and nitrous oxide release in European conservation agriculture: a meta-analysis

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This appendix lists the digital platforms used for literature retrieval. The resources span multidisciplinary databases, agricultural-specific repositories, and major academic publishers.

Name	Focus Area	Access Type	URL
Web of Science	Multidisciplinary	Subscription	https://www.webofscience.com/wos/wosc/basic-search
Scopus	Multidisciplinary	Subscription	https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus
AGRICOLA (USDA National Agricultural Library)	Agriculture	Free	https://www.nal.usda.gov/agricola
ScienceDirect	Science & Technology	Subscription	https://www.elsevier.com/products/sciencedirect
AGRIS (FAO)	Agriculture	Free	https://www.fao.org/agris/
Google Scholar	Multidisciplinary	Free	https://scholar.google.com/
Oxford University Press Journals	Multidisciplinary	Subscription	https://academic.oup.com/journals/
SpringerLink	Multidisciplinary	Subscription	https://link.springer.com/
Taylor & Francis Online	Multidisciplinary	Subscription	https://taylorandfrancis.com/online/taylor-francis-online/
Wiley Online Library	Multidisciplinary	Subscription	https://www.wiley.com/en-gb/
MDPI	Multidisciplinary	Open Access	https://www.mdpi.com/
Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)	Multidisciplinary	Open Access	https://doaj.org/